

EFFECTS OF LEVELED BOOKS ON THE READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE 4 LEARNERS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of leveled books in the reading comprehension of Grade 4 learners in English at LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo, Inc., during the school year 2020-2021. Before the use of the leveled books, the reading comprehension level of the Grade 4 learners as revealed in the pre-oral reading test results for the Independent level was 38.46, for Instructional readers 38.46, and for the Frustration level was 23.08 percent. Thus, using leveled books in reading comprehension was an effective tool in enhancing reading comprehension levels when the Grade 4 learners became Independent readers as revealed in the post-oral reading test results. Leveled books may be used by teachers as a tool to improve reading comprehension levels.

Keywords. Leveled Books, Reading Comprehension Level, English, Reading Level

1 Introduction

The Department of Education in the Philippines started implementing the K-12 Program in the school year 2012 as the key to the Nation's development and to produce globally competitive learners. To become a 21st-century skilled learner, a learner must excel in the four major skills of language which are speaking, listening, reading, and writing. This set of capabilities allows an individual to comprehend and produce spoken language for proper and effective interpersonal communication, Morehouse (2017).

To support the implementation of the Reading Recovery and the administration of the Philippine- Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), DepEd Order 10, s.2011 was issued and implemented which dealt with the guidelines on the utilization of funds for Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP). The Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) is a national program that supports the thrust of the Department of Education (DepEd) to make every learner a reader and writer at his/her grade level. It supports the attainment of the Education for All (EFA) target of universal school participation and elimination of dropouts and repetition in the first three- grades.

The Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) first measured the reading proficiency level in both English and Filipino of public elementary learners. The results of the assessment tool will serve as a basis for designing appropriate interventions at the school, division, regional, and national levels to enable every learner to read and write at his grade level.

According to the Department of Education, Every Child A Reader Program aims to equip elementary learners in public schools with strategic reading and writing skills to make them independent young readers and writers. The intervention program includes Reading Recovery (RR) which will give learners who are lagging in reading and writing a chance to catch up through specialized one-to-one reading assistance from a teacher trained in reading recovery procedures.

In LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo, Inc., some learners were given a particular leveled book fit to their grade level. Difficulty in reading was being observed as the teacher used the leveled books from Levels L to P for the Grade 4 learners including the titles Valentine's Day, Rainbows, Coding Camp, All about Chocolate, and Becky Puzzle Problem which the Directress of the stated school makes way to enhance the reading comprehension of every learner at their young age. Learners struggle when they cannot find the right answer to a question because learner cannot understand the idea or thought that is floated in the piece or story they were reading about. As a follow-up for their reading skills, the teacher uses these leveled books that are readily printed in the library and it assesses the reading comprehension level of a learner to focus on before proceeding to the next.

The assigned leveled books for the Grade 4 learners in the fourth quarter were the leveled books from L to P with the given titles, Valentine's Day, Rainbows, Coding Camp, All about Chocolate, and Becky Puzzle Problem. These leveled books were taken from the Fountas and Pinnell benchmark assessment system to measure the accuracy of the learners whether Independent, Instructional, or Frustration. In the Philippine- Informal Reading Inventory, there were three reading comprehension levels. Independent with a percentage of 80-100%, Instructional from 70-79 %. Lastly, Frustration with a percentage of 69% and below. These reading comprehension levels were similar to the Fountas and Pinnell reading comprehension level benchmark assessment criteria from leveled L to Z. For the Independent level its percentage is 98-100%, Instructional 95- 97%, and the term "Frustration" from the Philippine- Informal Reading Inventory has changed to "Hard" in the Fountas and Pinnell benchmark assessment criteria with a percentage of below 95%. Comprehension is very important in reading because it helps people view the meaning of the content.

2 Review of Related Literature

The review of related studies provides an adequate insight into the concept of the present study. They served as a guide on how to go about the investigation. The first thing we considered from the synthesis of related studies is the word "comprehension" as detailed by Al-Khaleeb (2014) that it is the peak of reading skills and the basics for all reading processes; by Baier (2015), learners who have good reading comprehension skills perform better in reading comprehension tests.

Secondly, the researcher will reflect on Sanford's (2015) adage that reading helps learners foster comprehension because as learners read longer passages they unify what they have read for the text. Hence, Ozdemir (2010) specified reading as fundamental in obtaining knowledge. Reading truly affects a learner's education depending on his understanding of what he reads in any lesson.

The current study is similar to Gillano (2014) who indicated the term that comes up when reading comprehension is being communicated. His respondents were considered under the instructional reading level which means learners benefit more from further reading instructions. These learners can read with assistance and proper guidance and are soon expected to be independent learners. Therefore, the present study sought to measure how effective were the leveled books from L to P with the titles Valentine's Day, Rainbows, Coding Camp, All about Chocolate, and Becky Puzzle Problem on the reading comprehension level of the Grade 4 learners of LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo Inc.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The researcher utilized descriptive design. Descriptive research is the research design in which data are collected qualitatively and analyzed using quantitative procedures (Nassaji, 2015). Descriptive research refers to the scientific methodology in which observation of the sampled population is carried out in its natural surroundings. Descriptive research methodology intends to find out 'what' is related to a phenomenon.

The descriptive method of the research described the pre-oral and post-oral reading comprehension level of the Grade 4 learners in English at LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo, Inc. during the school year 2020-2021.

3.2 Sources of Data

This study was conducted at LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo Inc., in Poblacion, Urbiztondo, Pangasinan. The respondents of the study are the thirteen (13) Grade 4 learners of LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo Inc., during the school year 2020-2021.

3.3 Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher requested permission from the director (School Head) of LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo Inc., to conduct the study. The pre-oral reading comprehension test was administered by the researcher to the thirteen (13) Grade 4 learners. The thirteen (13) Grade 4 learners were scheduled into three batches. The first batch was composed of 4 learners, 2 in the morning and another 2 learners in the afternoon. The same process to the second batch but for the third batch, it includes 5 learners where 3 learners took the 40-item pre-oral reading comprehension test in the morning and other

learners in the afternoon. This was made through a home face-to-face visit for three days to meet the thirteen (13) Grade 4 learners following the health protocols mandated by the Inter-Agency Task Force. After getting the scores of the pre and post-oral reading comprehension test the comprehension level of the learners was computed. After the pre-oral reading comprehension test, the reading comprehension level of the learners was identified. Then a post-oral reading comprehension test was administered to the Grade 4 learners using the same test items given in the pre-oral reading comprehension test.

The content of the pre and post-oral reading tests covering the leveled books from level L to P was used to identify the Independent, Instructional, and Frustration readers. The data gathering instrument used in the study in determining the reading comprehension level of the Grade 4 learners was the 40-item teacher-made test taken from the Fountas and Pinnell benchmark assessment system similar to the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory of the Department of Education that has the reading levels of Independent, Instructional, and Frustration

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Reading Comprehension Level Revealed in the Pre-Oral Reading Results

Table 1. Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 4 Learners as Revealed by PreOral Reading Results
 N=13

Reading Comprehension Level	Frequency(<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Independent	5	38.46
Instructional	5	38.46
Frustration	3	23.08
Total:	13	100

The table discloses that 38.46% of the Grade 4 learners' reading comprehension level is independent, and the other 38.46% are under instructional readers. This implies that most of the Grade 4 learners can read with a little assistance. As indicated by Murcia (2014) reading cannot be separated from comprehension because the purpose of the reading activity is to comprehend what has been read. Al-Khaleeb (2014) specified reading comprehension as the real core of the reading process. For Richard (2015) reading means perceiving a written text to understand its context. This can be done silently. It is a particular way in which the learners understand text messages, paragraphs, and books to gather information.

4.2 Reading Comprehension Level Revealed in the Post-Oral Reading Results

Table 2 discloses that all learners under the study were independent readers. It affirms having a mean comprehension score of 100 (in %) which is described as Independent. This reveals that the Grade 4 learners performed better and gained an Independent level of reading comprehension as compared to their pre-oral reading results. The reading comprehension level of the learners under frustration and instructional readers was developed through the use of the leveled books from L to P with the titles of Valentine's Day, Rainbows, Coding Camp, All about Chocolate, and Becky Puzzle Problem that were based on Fountas and Pinnell Benchmark Assessment System.

Table 2. Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 4 Learners as Revealed by Post-Oral Reading Results
 N=13

Reading Comprehension Level	Frequency(<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Independent	13	100
Instructional	0	0
Frustration	0	0
Total:	13	100

Lee (2014), in his article "How to Increase Reading Speed and Comprehension" mentioned three (3) useful tips to become a better and faster reader. One of which is: Knowing your vocabulary. This means that if you don't have an extensive vocabulary, you will have a more challenging time resolving and understanding the text. Another tip is to read a lot of books. According to Lee, those who read a lot of books as learners have an easier time reading and understanding text compared to those who barely touch their books. The last tip is to relate it to yourself. Baier (2015) hypothesized that learners who have good reading comprehension skills perform better in reading comprehension tests.

4.3 Comparison of Pre-Oral Reading and Post-Oral Reading Performance of the Grade 4 Learners

Table 2 shows the distribution of pre-oral and post-oral reading comprehension levels of the learners. The results show that there was an increase in their performance level in the post-oral reading tests.

Table 2. Comparison of the Pre-Oral and Post-Oral Reading Comprehension Test Results

N=13

Reading Comprehension Level	Pre-Oral Reading Comprehension Test Results	Post-Oral Reading Comprehension Test Results
Independent	5	13
Instructional	5	0
Frustration	3	0
Total:	13	13

All learners performed better after using the leveled books as revealed in the post-oral reading test results. The pre-oral reading results indicate that before the learners used the leveled books majority of them, 3 were under Frustration level and 5 under Instructional which reflects that they need assistance in reading and have difficulty in reading and understanding the written text. However, due to the use of the leveled books, the learners gained an Independent level as disclosed by the post-oral reading results which indicates that using leveled books was an effective strategy.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

There are 5 learners under the independent level and 5 learners who were under the instructional level. Only 3 of the total number of learners were under frustration level. Thus, the reading comprehension level of the Grade 4 learners as revealed in the pre-oral reading for the Independent level was 38.46, Instructional readers with 38.46, and the Frustration level was 23.08 percent.

The reading comprehension level of the Grade 4 learners as revealed in the post-oral reading comprehension test was 100 % which was described as Independent level. It has been observed that the leveled books used in the post-oral reading comprehension test were truly effective in enhancing reading comprehension amongst the Grade 4 learners. There is an evident increase in the performance of the Grade 4 learners from pre-oral reading comprehension test having 5 learners in the levels of Independent and Instructional and 3 learners at Frustration. Post-oral reading comprehension test that shows a total of 13 learners that lie on the Independent level having a percentage score of 100 (%).

A typical Grade 4 learner in LEAD Academy of Urbiztondo, Inc. has a reading comprehension level classified as Instructional. The reading comprehension level of Grade 4 learners would be enhanced using the leveled books. Leveled books are effective reading material in improving the reading comprehension level of Grade 4 learners.

Leveled books should be used to enhance the reading comprehension level of learners. Teachers should provide different materials in reading which can be an avenue to promote and make learners enjoy reading. Leveled books effectively help learners enhance their reading comprehension level, particularly in the English subject. Further studies should be conducted to include other factors that affect the reading comprehension level among learners.

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